

On the Ionisation of Some Polymeric Carboxylic Acids

B. N. Ghosh

Assuming that the hydrogen atom of a $-COOH$ group is linked with the CO of the neighbouring carboxyl group by hydrogen bond and that the proton will have to sever simultaneously two bonds to dissociate itself from the molecule of the polyacid and that for its combination with the molecule it will have to establish simultaneously two links, one with a COO^- group and the other with a free CO group, both of which must lie next to each other, certain equations have been deduced. These equations can account for, in a fairly satisfactory manner, the increase in the degree of dissociation and equivalent conductance with dilution of the solutions of polyacrylic acid and hydrolysed copolymer of maleic anhydride and styrene.

Electrical properties of polymers containing carboxyl groups, such as, polyacrylic acid, have been investigated by a number of authors¹⁻⁷. Only those polymeric acids, carboxyl groups of which are spaced in the molecular skeleton sufficiently close to each other to interact, have been considered in this communication and an attempt has been made to develop a theory to account for their ionisation in pure water.

Kern¹ proposed the following equation:

$$pH = pk_m + n \log \frac{\alpha_1}{1 - \alpha_1} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

for weak polymeric acids, where k_m and α_1 represent the "medium titration constant" and the degree of neutralisation respectively and n is a number which varies with the nature of the acid. This empirical equation has proved very useful in accounting for the titration curves of weak polymer acids with alkali.

Let us consider a solution which contains N_0 molecules of the weak polymer acid in a volume, V . Let each molecule contain S carboxyl groups and at equilibrium let n of these carboxyl groups ionise. Then the number of unionised carboxyl groups per molecule is $(S-n)$. We shall use the term, proton, for the H atom of an unionised carboxyl group. It is now assumed that the proton of a carboxyl group is linked by hydrogen bond with the CO group of the neighbouring carboxyl group in the molecule. Then the number of such linked CO groups is equal to the number of unionised carboxyl groups in each molecule.

In order that a proton may dissociate from a molecule, it will have to sever simultaneously two links, one with its own carboxyl group and the other with the neighbouring

1. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1939, A 181, 249, 283; *Biochem. Z.*, 1939, 301, 338.
2. Katchalsky and Spitnick, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1947, 2, 432.
3. Katchalsky and Gills, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1948, 68, 879.
4. Wall and DeButts, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1949, 17, 1330.
5. Kagawa and Katusuura, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1951, 7, 89.
6. Garrett and Gulie, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4531.
7. Wagner and Long, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1512.

CO group. The probability of such an event is obviously proportional to $[(S-n)/S]^2$. Therefore the rate of dissociation of a proton from a molecule of the acid should be expressed as $K_1[(S-n)/S]^2$, where K_1 is the rate constant.

Similarly for its combination with a molecule of the acid, an H^+ ion will have to establish simultaneously two links, one with a COO^- group and another with a free CO group, both of which must lie next to each other. The probability of such an event is proportional to $(n/S)^2$, since the number of free CO groups is equal to the number of COO^- groups per molecule. Therefore the rate of combination of hydrogen ions with a molecule of the acid should be written as

$$K_2 \left(\frac{n}{S} \right)^2 (H)$$

where (H) represents the concentration of the hydrogen ions in the solution and K_2 a constant. At equilibrium we have

$$K_2 \left(\frac{n}{S} \right)^2 (H) = K_1 \left(\frac{S-n}{S} \right)^2$$

Therefore

$$(H) = \frac{K_1}{K_2} \left(1 - \frac{n}{S} \right)^2 / (n/S)^2 = K \frac{(1-\alpha)^2}{(\alpha)^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $K = K_1/K_2$ and $(n/S) = \alpha$, the degree of ionisation. Equation (2) can also be written as

$$pH = pK + 2 \log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \quad \dots (3)$$

It will be noticed that equation (3) is of the same form as equation (1), but the n in equation (1) has been replaced by 2 in equation (3) and the significance of α_1 is not the same as that of α .

Writing $N_0 S/NV = C$, the concentration of the acid in gram equivalents, N being the Avogadro number, we have $\alpha C = (H)$. Solving equation (2) for α , we get

$$\alpha = \frac{\sqrt{K}}{\sqrt{K} + \sqrt{(H)}} \quad \dots (4)$$

or

$$\alpha C = (H) = \frac{C\sqrt{K}}{\sqrt{K} + \sqrt{(H)}} \quad \dots (5)$$

It follows from equation (5) that

$$\frac{C}{\sqrt{(H)}} = 1 + \frac{\sqrt{(H)}}{\sqrt{K}} \quad \dots (6)$$

Therefore, according to equation (6), when the weak polymer acid is diluted, a plot of $C/\sqrt{(H)}$ against $\sqrt{(H)}$ will be linear and the slope of the straight line will be equal to $1/\sqrt{K}$.

Again, writing αC for (H) in equation (5) the following expression is obtained:

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = 1 + \frac{\sqrt{\alpha C}}{\sqrt{K}} \quad \dots (7)$$

For a weak polymer acid, if it be assumed that $\alpha = \lambda/\lambda_0$, where λ is the equivalent conductance at concentration C and λ_0 is the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution, equation (7) can be written as

$$\frac{\lambda_0}{\lambda} = 1 + \frac{\sqrt{C\lambda}}{\sqrt{\lambda_0 K}} \quad (8)$$

Thus in those cases, where equation (8) is followed, a plot of $1/\lambda$ against $\sqrt{C\lambda}$ will be linear.

Equations (6) and (8) have been subjected to test, using the data of Kern¹ on polyacrylic acid and of Wall and DeButts⁴ on the hydrolysed copolymer of maleic anhydride and styrene.

DISCUSSION

In Fig. 1 the curve of $C/(H)$ has been plotted against the corresponding values of $\sqrt{(H)}$, using the data obtained by Kern¹ on the polyacrylic acid, $P = 900$, and in Fig. 2 are represented similarly the data of Wall and DeButts⁴. In both the cases the plot is linear and is thus in agreement with the theory.

FIG. 1. Polyacrylic acid.

FIG. 2. Hydrolysed copolymer of maleic acid and styrene.

Wall and DeButts⁴ have used in their calculation of equivalent conductance a value of concentration, C , of the polymer, which is tenth of that recorded in column 1 of Table I of their paper. We have found that this reduced values of C provide nearly the correct intercept on the $C/(H)$ axis as required by equation (6). Therefore, the values of C , referred to above, must have been expressed in an arbitrary unit. The value of K for the acids can be easily calculated from the slope of the straight lines.

In Figs. 3 and 4 are plotted $1/\lambda$ against $\sqrt{C\lambda}$, using the data taken from the papers of Kern¹ and Wall and DeButts⁴, referred to above. It will be noticed that the relation-

ship between $1/\lambda$ and $\sqrt{C\lambda}$ is linear except at the highest values of the concentration used. Since the conductance of the polymeric acids is due almost entirely to that of the hydrogens

FIG. 3. Polyacrylic acid.

FIG. 4. Hydrolysed copolymer of maleic acid and styrene.

ions, it may be assumed that at high concentration, the skeletons of the polymer molecules offer obstruction to the flow of current and this affects the cell constant. Ghosh and Pal⁸ have shown that in such cases a correction should be applied and the factor is of the form $(1 + \frac{m \langle C \rangle}{1 - \langle C \rangle})$, where m is a constant and $\langle C \rangle / (1 - \langle C \rangle)$ represents the ratio of the volume of solid to that of the liquid in the solution. In the present case, $\langle C \rangle$ in the denominator may be neglected and the correct value of equivalent conductance may

be found by using the approximate expression:

$$\lambda_r = \lambda (1 + aC)$$

where a is a constant for a given polymer sample. If a is put equal to 1.25 and C is taken the same, as recorded by Wall and DeButts⁴ (*vide supra*), and the correct values of $1/\lambda_r$ and $\sqrt{C\lambda_r}$ are plotted, then the two extreme points in Fig. 4, corresponding to two high values of C , also fall on the straight line.

It may therefore be concluded that the equations (6) and (8) are in fair agreement with the data of Kern on polyacrylic acid and of Wall and DeButts on hydrolysed copolymer of maleic anhydride and styrene.